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Review Article

***In Silico* Molecular Modeling Studies on Novel Imidazole Derivatives and Their Potential Anti-Tubercular Activities Utilizing Advanced CADD Tools**

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ABSTRACT

Tuberculosis or TB, is extremely contagious diseases globally that can affect the life of people. Historically, it was regarded as an epidemic. Although TB is now treatable, many patients still endure long-term suffering, and some may die from the disease. The primary causative agent is a gram-positive bacterium called Mycobacterium tuberculosis. Studying novel anti-tubercular agents is essential for effective TB treatment. The bacteria spread through the air via droplets released when an infected person coughs, sneezes, or speaks. Others can inhale these droplets, leading to the transmission of the disease. The most important cum common symptoms of TB are chest pain, tightness chest, coughing up blood, fever, dry cough, and continuous weight loss. Multiple studies have examined the pathophysiology of TB and the receptors involved in the disease. Directly Observed Therapy (DOT) is available, utilizing first- and second-line antibiotics for long-term treatment. Resistance develops when patients stop taking their medications without medical supervision or when the bacteria become resistant due to prolonged exposure to treatments. This study primarily focuses on in silico molecular modeling and drug discovery of novel substituted imidazole derivatives to evaluate their potential anti-tubercular activities. A comprehensive approach has been undertaken, including molecular docking, pharmacokinetic analysis, and toxicity profiling. Ongoing research aims to design newer molecules using in silico computer-aided drug design (CADD) methodologies. This paper highlights research studies related to the discovery of new imidazole-substituted compounds through in silico molecular modeling techniques.

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INTRODUCTION

Mycobacterium tuberculosis causes tuberculosis, a communicable bacterial infection that primarily affects the lungs before spreading to other organs. This disease has not been completely overcome yet, and one-third of the world's population still suffers from it. The scenario regarding TB has worsened since the COVID-19 pandemic, as many patients' health has been compromised during and after their COVID infection. The *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* can attack these patients, whose immune systems have become very weak, putting them at a higher risk of infection. Additionally, some drugs are becoming ineffective against TB because COVID-19 treatment often involves various medications, including some TB drugs. As a result, first line and second line antibiotics for TB may no longer be effective due to the body developing resistance. It's also reported that patients who were diagnosed with TB early but took a long time to recover might face complications. While the initial infection can be cured, subsequent infections may not respond to the same medications, as the bacteria may resist treatment through chemotherapeutic classification. This highlights why tuberculosis remains a critical public health issue today, which is why I have chosen to focus on TB. There is nothing new about TB; it is caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, with symptoms including coughing up blood, sneezing, fatigue, fever, weight loss, chest pain, and loss of appetite. It is usually identified by several sputum tests and chest X-rays. Different countries like India (28%), Indonesia (9.2%), China (7.4%), and Philippines

(7.0%) are having highest data in associated with TB. While only a small percentage of those with latent tuberculosis infection (LTBI) progress to active TB, approximately 10 million individuals have fallen ill with this disease each year since 2000. The mortality rate is equally alarming, with an estimated 1.4 to over 2 million lives lost annually from 2000 to 2021. According to previous report, TB symptoms present exceed than a million in the year of 2021. 1.4 million individuals from HIV-negative and 0.2 million individuals from HIV-positive were also affected by TB. Importantly, before the COVID-19 pandemic, TB fatalities consistently surpassed those caused by any other single infectious agent, including HIV/AIDS. This stark reality highlights the urgent and immediate need for sustained action against this preventable and treatable disease. [1, 2]

Existing Treatment of Tuberculosis:

The standard treatment for drug-sensitive tuberculosis (TB) is a six-month regimen of four key medications: isoniazid, rifampicin, ethambutol, and pyrazinamide. For drug resistant TB, treatment is individualized based on resistance profiles and typically involves longer durations and additional medications, demonstrating a strong commitment to patient care.[1,2]

First Line Anti TB Drugs: [3-4]

Some existing drugs with more efficacy and lower side effects are useful to treat multidrug sensitive TB.

Table 1: First Line Anti TB Drugs

Drug Name	Abbreviation	Remarks
Isoniazid	(INH)	Bactericidal; important for latent and active TB
Rifampin	(RIF)	Broad-spectrum; turns body fluids orange
Ethambutol	(EMB)	Bacteriostatic; used to prevent resistance
Pyrazinamide	(PZA)	Works best in acidic environments (inside macrophages)

Second Line Anti TB Drugs: [5-7]

These are used when TB is resistant to first-line drugs, especially in MDR-TB (Multidrug

Resistant TB) and XDR-TB (Extensively Drug Resistant TB) cases. They are often less effective, more toxic, and more expensive.

Table 2: Second Line Anti TB Drugs - Fluoroquinolones (core second-line agents)

Fluoroquinolones (core second-line agents)	Abbreviation	Remarks
Moxifloxacin	(MOX)	Bactericidal; potent activity against <i>M. tuberculosis</i> . Used in MDR-TB and sometimes in shorter regimens.
Levofloxacin	(LFX)	Bactericidal; slightly less potent than Moxifloxacin. Used in MDR-TB treatment
Ofloxacin (less preferred now)	(OFX)	Older generation, less potent. Still used in some MDR-TB regimens where newer drugs are unavailable.

Table 3: Second Line Anti TB Drugs - Injectable Agents (used less often now)

Injectable Agents (used less often now)	Abbreviation	Remarks
Amikacin	(AMK)	Bactericidal – inhibits protein synthesis by binding to the 30S ribosomal subunit.
Capreomycin	(CAP)	Bacteriostatic or bactericidal; inhibits protein synthesis
Kanamycin	(KAN)	Similar to amikacin.
Streptomycin- once first line, now mainly used in special cases	(SM)	Bactericidal – inhibits protein synthesis. It was used for TB before rifampicin.

Table 4: Second Line Anti TB Drugs - Newer Drugs

Newer Drugs	Abbreviation	Remarks
Bedaquiline	(BDQ)	newer, used in MDR/XDR-TB
Linezolid	(LZD)	also effective in MDR/XDR-TB
Clofazimine	(CFZ)	originally for leprosy
Cycloserine	(CS)	Second line agent
Delamanid	(DLM)	Newer drug, for MDR-TB
Pretomanid	(Pa)	used in the BPaLM regimen

Multidrug Resistance of Anti TB Drugs:

Multidrug resistant TB is very critical form of TB in where maximum existing drugs are tolerated and resistant to TB causative organism like *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* strains.

1. Isoniazid (INH)

2. Rifampin (RIF)

These are the two most powerful first-line anti-TB drugs, so resistance makes the infection much harder to treat. [4-8]

Causes of MDR-TB [8-9]:

Table 5: Causes of MDR-TB

Cause	Explanation
Incomplete or irregular treatment	Missing doses, stopping treatment early, or poor drug quality
Inappropriate drug prescription	Wrong combinations or dosages by healthcare providers
Poor absorption	Especially in HIV patients or those with GI issues
Transmission from others	Person-to-person spread of already resistant TB

Pathophysiology of Tuberculosis:

Tuberculosis (TB) Stages:

1. Primary Infection
2. Latent Infection
3. Active Infection

Mycobacterium tuberculosis causes initial infections, with around 95% being asymptomatic. Only 5-10% progress to active disease.

Primary TB infection: It occurs through inhaling small particles that reach the lungs. A single droplet can initiate infection. Once inside alveolar macrophages, bacilli may replicate, leading to macrophage death and inflammation. TB germ enters into local lymph nodes and accumulates in the whole body. At this stage, TB is not communicable.

Latent TB Infection: Most primary infections become latent, with the immune system suppressing bacillary growth within three weeks. TB germ converted into granulomas for many

years. Latent sites are active, not entirely dormant. IGRA and tuberculin skin tests are having the results of positive during this part of disease. Sometimes, primary infections can cause severe illness, particularly in young or immunosuppressed individuals. Extrapulmonary TB can occur without lung involvement, with lymphadenopathy being the most common form. At this stage, TB is not communicable.

Active TB Disease: Healthy individuals have a 5-10% lifetime risk of developing active TB, especially within the first two years. Reactivation commonly occurs in the lungs but can also affect other organs. Impaired immunity significantly increases reactivation risk. For instance, HIV co-infected patients not on therapy have a 10% annual risk of active TB. Other risk factors include diabetes, head and neck cancer, and chronic kidney disease. Awareness of these stages and risk factors is essential for effective TB diagnosis, treatment, and prevention. [10-11]

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

a) Software and Web servers: [12-25]

Pub Chem

Protein Data Bank (PDB)

CB-DOCK2

Auto Dock Tools

Swiss ADME

Pharmit

b) Methods:

Figure 1: Methodology

Lipinski's rule: [26]

- 1) The total number of hydrogen bond donors must be within five.
- 2) The total number of hydrogen bond acceptors must be within ten.

3) There should be no more than 500 Daltons of molecular mass.

4) Log P needs to be fewer than five.

RESULTS

Table 6: List of Standard Compound

Sl. No.	Name of Standard Compound	Structure
1	Delamanid	

Figure 2: Cyclopropane Mycolic Acid Synthase 1 (1KPG)

Table 7: List of Test Samples

SL.No.	Test Samples	Structure
1	Test Sample 1	
2	Test Sample 2	

3	Test Sample 3	
4	Test Sample 4	
5	Test Sample 5	

6	Test Sample 6	
7	Test Sample 7	
8	Test Sample 8	
9	Test Sample 9	

10	Test Sample 10	

Table 8: Receptor Activate Site (Coordinates)

Receptor	X	Y	Z
Cyclopropane mycolic acid synthase 1 (PDB Code: 1KPG)	49.696	36.6161	55.0437

Sl. No.	Name of the Standard Compound	Docking Result [Binding Energy (kcal/mol)]	Molecular Docking
1	Delamanid	-11.8	

Table 10: Molecular Docking of Test Samples to the Active Sites of 1KPG

Sl. No.	Name of the Test Samples	Docking Result [Binding Energy (kcal/mol)]	Molecular Docking
1.	Test Sample 1	-25.2	
2.	Test Sample 2	-13.2	
3.	Test Sample 3	-12.5	
4.	Test Sample 4	-12.2	

5.	Test Sample 5	-12.1	
6	Test Sample 6	-12.0	
7	Test Sample 7	-10.9	

8	Test Sample 8	-10.7	
9	Test Sample 9	-10.6	
10	Test Sample 10	-10.5	

Figure 3: Graphical Plot for Molecular Docking of Standard and Test Samples to the Active Site of 1KPG (The orange indicates the test sample that has more binding energy than the standard compound)

Table 11: Pharmacophoric Features of Screened Test Sample Based on Molecular Docking

Test Sample	Pharmacophoric Structure	Features	No. of Features
Test Sample 1		Aromatic, Hydrogen Acceptor, Hydrophobic, Negative ion, Positive ion	6

Table 12: Lipinski's rule for Filtration of Standard Compound

Sl. No.	Compound	Formula	Molecular Weight [g/mol] <500	iLOG P <5	H-Donor <5	H-Acceptor <10	Molar Refractivity (MR)	Rotatable Bonds	Lipinski's Rule Following
1	Delamanid	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ F ₃ N ₄ O ₆	534.48	3.71	0	10	134.50	9	Yes 1 Violation (MW>500)

Table 13: Lipinski's rule for Filtration of Test Samples

Sl. No.	Test Samples	Formula	Molecular Weight [g/mol] <500	iLOG P <5	H-Donor <5	H-Acceptor <10	Molar refractivity (MR)	Rotatable Bonds	Lipinski's Rule Following
1	Test Sample 1	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₄	358.4	2.73	0	6	101.80	5	Yes
2	Test Sample 2	C ₂₆ H ₂₇ F ₃ N ₄ O ₆	548.5	3.92	0	11	138.86	10	Yes 1 Violation (MW>500)
3	Test Sample 3	C ₂₇ H ₂₈ F ₃ N ₅ O ₅	559.5	4.19	0	11	149.72	10	Yes 1 Violation (MW>500)
4	Test Sample 4	C ₂₈ H ₂₉ F ₃ N ₄ O ₄	542.5	4.14	0	9	146.03	9	Yes 1 Violation (MW>500)
5	Test Sample 5	C ₂₂ H ₂₉ N ₅ O ₆	459.5	3.41	0	7	129.55	8	Yes, 1 violation:
6	Test Sample 6	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ F ₃ N ₅ O ₅ S	509.5	3.28	2	9	124.96	10	Yes 1 Violation (MW>500)
7	Test Sample 7	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₆	439.42	2.46	2	7	117.57	9	Yes, 1 violation:
8	Test Sample 8	C ₂₄ H ₂₅ ClN ₄ O ₅	484.93	3.64	0	6	132.83	7	Yes 0 Violation
9	Test Sample 9	C ₂₅ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₅	464.51	3.58	0	6	132.78	7	Yes 0 Violation
10	Test Sample 10	C ₂₅ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₆	480.51	3.58	0	7	134.31	8	Yes 0 Violation

Table 14: ADMET of Screened Standard Compound

Compound	GI Absorption	BBB Permeation	Water Solubility	Pgp Substrate	Skin Permeability log Kp (cm/s)
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Standard Compound	Low	No	Poorly Soluble	No	-5.56
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Table 15: ADME of Screened Test Samples

Test Sample	Test Parameters				
	GI Absorption	BBB Permeation	Water Solubility	Pgp Substrate	Skin Permeability log Kp (cm/s)
Test Sample 1	High	No	Moderately Soluble	Yes	-6.31
Test Sample 2	Low	No	Poorly Soluble	No	-5.88
Test Sample 3	High	No	Poorly Soluble	No	-5.91
Test Sample 4	Low	No	Poorly Soluble	Yes	-5.02
Test Sample 5	High	No	Moderately Soluble	No	-7.05
Test Sample 6	Low	No	Poorly Soluble	No	-6.25
Test Sample 7	High	No	Moderately Soluble	Yes	-7.11
Test Sample 8	High	No	Poorly Soluble	No	-5.65
Test Sample 9	High	No	Poorly Soluble	No	-5.72
Test Sample 10	High	No	Poorly Soluble	No	-6.09

CONCLUSION

Tuberculosis (TB) is a highly contagious disease that poses a significant global health threat. While vaccination is now available, TB continues to affect many people worldwide. In light of this, we have identified 50 compounds and screened ten compounds among them according to their binding energy and docking analysis. We also generated pharmacophoric features and performed Lipinski's rule filtration. As a result, test molecule 1 shows better response due to their high binding energy, favorable pharmacophoric features, and compliance with all ADME parameters, as well as the Lipinski's rule. This molecule show more potentiality as a target for tuberculosis treatment.

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